

Treating heart attacks with blood thinners

What do patients PREFER?

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Patient preferences for blood thinners

A myocardial infarction, or what is commonly known as a ‘heart attack’, happens when the large blood vessels that support the heart (known as the coronary arteries) are blocked and a part of the heart is deprived of oxygen. The blockage of your arteries is caused by a buildup of blood fats (cholesterol) and other substances in the artery walls. Without oxygen, muscle cells in the heart begin to die, which means you need to have medical treatment as soon as possible.

You need to treat the buildup in your arteries to prevent new heart attacks and, if blood flow to the brain is blocked, it can lead to a stroke and cause problems with your thinking, memory, and speech. If there is severe blockage of your arteries, you can also die.

To reduce blockage in your arteries, heart attack treatments include medicines that thin your blood to prevent further harm. But because these treatments thin your blood, they can also cause bleeding. In some cases, the bleeding can be very severe and you might need emergency care and a blood transfusion.

We have asked patients who have had a heart attack about their preferences when it comes to heart attack medications.

When we study preferences, we look at how a person is choosing between different options and circumstances.

We wanted to know how much value a person gives different risks and benefits of a particular treatment, and how they balance between them.

We also wanted to know if there is a difference between patient preferences in the **acute stage** (when receiving treatment during emergency medical care in a hospital or soon after discharge) and what is called the **chronic stage** (after leaving the hospital when the patients' condition is more stable).

Who answered our questions?

In this study, we asked more than 300 patients about their preferences- approximately half in the acute stage and half in the chronic stage of their disease.

Most of them were men, on average, 64 years old. Many of the patients also had other medical conditions, like high cholesterol, high blood pressure, or diabetes, and several of them had already used medicines that thin the blood.

All patients had been hospitalized after a heart-attack, they were over 18 and living in England.

What did we find out?

There is **no difference** between how patients balance the risks and benefits of blood thinning medicines soon after the heart attack (during the acute stage) and after they have left the hospital and their conditions have stabilized (during the chronic stage).

Patients were most concerned about the increased risk of severe bleeding, and we could see that it affected how they balance that risk against benefits of the medicine, like reducing the risk of dying, or having another heart attack or stroke.

We also could see that **preferences depended on different factors** such as age. For example, patients who were older were more likely to choose a treatment that reduces the risk of another heart attack than younger patients.

Why is this research important?

The results from our research can help pharmaceutical companies decide which drugs to continue to develop.

For example, if a company is developing two blood thinners: 'drug A' and 'drug B' and drug A is less likely to cause severe bleeding than drug B, these results could help the company decide which of the medicines they should continue to develop. Since drug A is more in line with the patients' preferences, the company may stop development of drug B. During the decision-making process, companies can also consider that no differences were observed between what patients prefer in the acute and chronic stages of their disease.

The results of the study may also be useful to other health authorities that approve medicines and decide what a particular medicine will cost.

How we did the research (methodology)

This research consisted of 2 parts: a pilot study (with interviews), and the main study (online survey). In a first **pilot study** we conducted initial interviews over the phone with ten patients: Both men and women, over 18, living in England and who had previously been admitted to hospital after a heart attack. Their answers helped us further develop the main survey. In the pilot study we asked the following questions:

- Do patients understand the questions they were going to be asked in the main study?
- Have we captured all the important treatment outcomes?

After the pilot study, we conducted an **online survey** with more than 300 patients, both men and women. We wanted to know two things:

- Do heart attack patients value treatment outcomes differently at different stages of their disease?
- Are there differences in terms of how they value these outcomes based on who they are (e.g. based on their age, medical history).

To take part in the study, patients had to meet the same requirements as the pilot study but, in the main study, there was no interview so telephone access was not required just access to a computer to complete the survey.

Want to know more about the study?

The PREFER project would like to thank all the patients that helped us in this research by answering the questions in our survey.

By participating in patient preference research, you can contribute information that can help the companies that develop medicines, the authorities that approve them (known as regulators), and the authorities that decide what becomes available for patients and the cost for patients.

The lead researchers who worked on this study are listed below. They can be reached if you have further questions about this study. More information about this research can be found at: <https://www.imi-prefer.eu/case-studies/myocardial-infarction/>. The results have also been published in a scientific journal:

Pinto, C.A., Chua, G.N., Bridges, J.F.P. et al. Comparing Patient Preferences for Antithrombotic Treatment During the Acute and Chronic Phases of Myocardial Infarction: A Discrete-Choice Experiment. Patient (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40271-021-00548-6>

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About this study

Study Identification: The study is registered (#210003-001) on the Health Preference Study and Technology Registry which can be accessed at: <https://hpstr.org/record/210003/001/013/entry>

Data Privacy and Ethics Approval: This study was conducted in accordance with General Data Privacy Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) and with ethics board approval (Bloomsbury research ethics committee and Health Research Authority [HRA]).

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PATIENT PREFERENCES

Want to know more? Go the PREFER project's website: www.imi-prefer.eu

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